

CoARA Boost

Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, including Communication Activities

Deliverable 7.1

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Abbreviations	
ARRA	Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CoP	Community of Practice
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NC	National Chapter
PoC	Point of Contact
OA	Open Access
RA	Research Assessment
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
R&I	Research and Innovation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RRA	Responsible Research Assessment
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Dissemination and Exploitation plan, including Communication activities (DEC) outlines the strategies and activities planned for the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) initiative within the framework of the CoARA Boost project. The CoARA Boost project strengthens CoARA's operational capacity. It provides a means to develop a critical mass for reforming research assessment, to generate gravitas for new members as well as to investigate and implement new models for research assessment. Over 700 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and their associations have agreed on a common direction and principles for reforming the assessment of research and have committed to implement changes within their organisations. The DEC strategy focuses on offering an outline of the platforms and activities that aim to raise awareness and engage a wide range of stakeholders to advance research assessment reform within an agreed timeline, as outlined in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment \(ARRA\)](#).

This document identifies the main objectives and target groups, as well as the communication, dissemination, engagement, and exploitation activities that are developed to facilitate collaboration among CoARA members and stakeholders towards the implementation of institutional change. It describes in detail the list of communications tools and dissemination and exploitation pathways developed to date and outlines future activations, matched with key performance indicators for reporting purposes.

1. Introduction

This Dissemination and Exploitation plan, including Communication activities (DEC), is both a strategic action plan to be implemented and a handbook for the consortium partners to support them in their dissemination, exploitation and communication efforts. Readers will find:

- An overview of the objectives and target audiences of the DEC plan, and CoARA's key communication messages
- A detailed list of communication tools
- Dissemination and exploitation pathways

As an initial strategy, it is complemented with the communication and advocacy plan to expand membership in M18 (D6.4) and will be implemented along the full period of the project.

1.1. CoARA Boost

The vision of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is that in the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognise the diverse outputs, practices, and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.

To achieve this vision, CoARA's mission is to enable systemic reform of research assessment based on common principles and commitments within an agreed timeframe, as set in the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. This also imparts the exchange of information and mutual learning between all those willing to improve research assessment practices.

The CoARA Boost project, funded by the European Union, catalyses CoARA's operational capacity and aims to make a significant contribution towards enabling a systemic reform of research assessment. CoARA Boost i) strengthens CoARA's operational capacity, ii) catalyses knowledge development, policy evolution, and institutional change in research assessment, iii) facilitates the collection and exchange of information, and iv) widens the coalition's membership in Europe and beyond. The project is crucial for the global growth of the reform-focused community, amplifying collaboration and enhancing knowledge exchange and mutual learning within the coalition. Further details on CoARA Boost's contribution to CoARA are available in CoARA Boost D1.1, on Project governance and procedures.

1.2. DEC Objectives

The main objectives of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, including Communication Activities, can be clustered as follows:

- i) **Raise awareness** about the need to reform research assessment, communicating CoARA's ambition and its members' commitments towards this common objective.
- ii) **Disseminate information** on institutional change and promote data, good practices, bottlenecks, and lessons learnt issued from mapping, WGs, and funded projects; share guidance and recommendations for uptake of results of core contributors to CoARA – including outputs from CoARA Boost – by research organisations, higher education institutions, and policymakers.
- iii) **Empower CoARA members and ARRA signatories** to efficiently communicate and disseminate their progress towards reform within their internal and external networks and **ensure a broad uptake and ownership** of CoARA's outputs and recommendations at a global level.

Complementing this plan, an Advocacy plan will be developed as part of “D6.4 Communication and advocacy plan for other projects and initiatives,” including tactics to promote efforts to reform research assessment at a global level, expand CoARA membership to all continents and advocate for the uptake of its recommendations by policymakers.

2. Target Audiences

CoARA's target audiences for this DEC strategy fall into three categories: key players, context setters and advocates. They are detailed hereafter.

2.1. Key players

Key players are actively involved in the reform of research assessment, and/or in implementing the ARRA commitments. They are CoARA Members, signatories of the ARRA, or are targeted to sign the ARRA and join the coalition.

2.1.1. CoARA Members and ARRA signatories

This core target group includes all CoARA member organisations and ARRA signatory

organisations, as “creators and consumers.” Within this group, CoARA Boost’s communication and dissemination activities are tailored to their level of involvement in the coalition, from key contributors to not-yet-involved members. Individuals addressed are mainly legal representatives and researchers involved in research assessment within these institutions.

- CoARA key contributor groups: member representatives involved WG and NC, SB and CoARA Boost consortium, cascade funding beneficiaries
- Non-involved member representatives

2.1.2. Potential members

Within the project’s planned efforts to expand CoARA’s membership at a global level, key stakeholders at European and global levels are identified and engaged to join the coalition. This target audience group is further detailed within D6.2 and D6.3, respectively a European and Global analysis report on less-represented countries and key stakeholders (M12).

2.2. Context setters

Context setters, mainly policymakers and advisory bodies, provide framework at national, EU, and international levels which shape research assessment and contribute to its reform. As recipients of CoARA’s recommendations and outputs, including CoARA Boost’s results, they will be addressed as a specific target audience group. While some context setters are part of CoARA member organisations and are included in the key player target audience group, many are not eligible for membership despite being robustly involved in the reform of research assessment, as is the case with ministries. Targets include:

- The European Commission: DG RTD, and most notably the DG’s Open Science Unit, Research Assessment team; all contributors to FP10
- European Research Area (ERA) Forum:
 - Policy Agenda 2022–2024 Action 3: “Reform the Assessment System for research, researchers and institutions”.
 - Policy Agenda 2022–2024 Action 4: “Promote attractive research careers, talent circulation and mobility”.
- Policy Agenda 2024–2026 Action 6 (the new ERA Policy Agenda has not yet been published at the current stage of this deliverable)
 - Council of the European Union
 - National level policymakers: research ministries, working groups, advisory bodies, national research assessment agencies and research councils.
 - Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)

2.3. Advocates

CoARA targets related initiatives, umbrella organisations, non-profit organisations and individuals to raise awareness about the need for research assessment reform and its work in progress towards reform. This target group of “Advocates” is primarily addressed as influencers on the previous groups.

2.3.1. Researchers

While individual researchers do not constitute CoARA’s primary target (unlike the DOARA initiative), as end-beneficiaries impacted by research assessment, they are aware of the need for reform and show a strong interest in the development of outputs issued from CoARA and CoARA Boost.

2.3.2. Member organisation stakeholders

CoARA Boost targets the appointed contacts of CoARA’s member organisations. To ensure a multiplying effect, it develops tactics for its members to communicate about their involvement in CoARA to all their staff members, particularly researchers and students, as well as their external stakeholders.

2.3.3. Umbrella organisations and networks

Organisations, associations and networks representing the interests of RPOs and RFOs are engaged throughout the project, as “advocates” towards their members and stakeholders, while also constituting end-beneficiaries. These include, although are not limited to:

- Science Europe (scienceeurope.org)
- EUA, European University Association (eua.eu)
- LERU (leru.org)
- YERUN (yerun.eu)
- Coimbra Group (coimbra-group.eu)
- The Guild (the-guild.eu)
- UNICA (unica-network.eu)
- CESAER (cesaer.org)
- ALLEA (allea.org)
- EARTO (earto.eu)
- EARMA (earma.org)

- ECIU (eciu.eu)
- EURASHE (eurashe.eu)
- EUHA (euhalliance.eu)
- UAS4EUROPE (uas4europe.eu)
- Erasmus + and Universities Research Alliances

2.3.4. Related projects and initiatives

CoARA leverages contacts with initiatives and projects developed at national, EU, and international levels related to the reform of research assessment. Synergies are specifically developed within WP6 and T6.1. A preliminary list of related projects and initiatives is listed hereafter and is completed with further information within D6.1 (submitted in M12).

- **EC-funded projects:**

CoARA builds on the results of projects funded under earlier and ongoing EU Framework Programme actions, relevant to the reform of research assessment, including those related to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and namely:

- [OPUS](#) - Open Universal Science
- [GraspOS](#) - Next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science
- [SciLake](#) - Democratising and making sense out of heterogeneous scholarly content
- [Skills4EOSC](#) - Skills for the European Open Science Commons: Creating a Training Ecosystem for Open and FAIR Science

- Projects funded under Horizon Europe:
 - [PATHOS](#): Open Science Impact Pathways.
 - [GENDERACTIONplus](#)
 - [DIAMAS](#)
 - [SECURE](#)
 - [aUPaEU](#)

- **Major international initiatives:**

This category pertains to programmes in the research assessment domain, aimed at positively influencing and advancing research assessment methodologies. In doing so, it recognises thematic overlaps and synergies within CoARA's objectives. Values and principles of these initiatives and frameworks resonate with CoARA's: openness, responsibility, collaboration and mutual support, inspiration, commitment, autonomy,

voluntary and community-driven, dialogue, inclusiveness, trust, and non-profit. The group's initiatives and frameworks are likely to align with specific objectives related to responsible research practices, principles of open and inclusive science, responsible application of evaluation metrics and development of new ones, enforcing standardised assessment frameworks, fostering research excellence and innovation, and accountability in research evaluation. Initiatives include, but are not limited to:

- DORA – Project TARA
 - Global Research Council – Responsible Research Assessment
 - UNESCO Activities on Open Science
 - G7 Expert Group on Open Science / Sub-group on Research Assessment
 - Altmetrics – Alternative Assessment Metrics
 - ERF – Research Infrastructures Facilities
 - INORMS SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation
 - Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics
 - Lindau Nobel Laureate Meetings
 - OpenCitations
 - SEP – Strategy Evaluation Protocol
 - The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers
 - cOAlition S
 - Research Data Alliance (RDA) and its related interest groups
 - The Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information
-
- **Related initiatives at national level**
 - UKRI (<https://www.ukri.org/>)
 - NAS Roundtable on Science
 - Norwegian NOR-CAM
 - Recognition & Rewards programme (recognitionrewards.nl)
 - REF – Research Excellence Framework (ref.ac.uk)

2.3.5. Research Assessment Experts

Researchers specialised in the field of research assessment are identified as a specific

target for taking up outputs from CoARA, including CoARA Boost, for further research.

2.3.6. Media

In addition to members' own media channels, CoARA Boost will address media outlets dedicated to research policy, addressing policymakers, academics, research administrators among others.

Publications dedicated to research and academic news

- Research Professional News – Research Europe
- Times Higher Education
- Inside Higher Ed
- The Chronicle of Higher Education
- Science Business
- Nature – policy section
- Science – policy forum
- The Scientist
- Science Careers (part of the Science journal)
- The London School of Economics Impact blog

General news outlets with specialised sections and digital high-reach platforms, will also be addressed, such as:

- Live Science
- ScienceDaily
- Wired – Science
- Vox – Science & Health
- The Conversation
- The Research Whisperer
- SciDev.Net

3. Communication and raising awareness

CoARA Boost enhances CoARA stakeholders' efforts in actively communicating about the need for research assessment reform, and the coalition's work towards achieving this reform. This involves:

- Building a common understanding about the need for research assessment reform and the commitments that CoARA's members are taking towards institutional change.
- Facilitating the efforts of CoARA members and ARRA signatories in raising awareness about their research assessment reform. Preparing the grounds for dissemination and advocacy by reinforcing networks and stimulating interest in the project's results.

3.1. Key Messages

The key messages communicated about CoARA are summarised hereafter and made available for all stakeholders to use.

The research community widely agrees on the need to reform how research, researchers, and institutions are assessed. Over reliance on publication-based metrics fail to recognise diverse contributions to research and can harm research quality and culture. CoARA provides a platform for organisations committed to systemic change, guided by the ARRA launched in July 2022, which sets principles and commitments for reform. CoARA fosters collaboration, mutual learning, and action through working groups and communities of practice to create a more inclusive, responsible, and diverse research assessment landscape.

Key Message	Context
<p>There is broad agreement from the research community on the urgent need to reform existing ways of assessing research. The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is broad agreement among research communities worldwide on the need to redefine how research, researchers, and research institutions are assessed. At present, assessment processes primarily rely on journal- and publication-based metrics: this can be a hurdle to the recognition of diverse contributions and may negatively affect the quality and impact of research. They also contribute to an unhealthy research culture and an unaffordable

<p>provides a common direction towards this goal. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) offers a platform for collaboration and mutual learning.</p>	<p>publication system.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In order to drive systemic reform of research assessment practices, there is an urgent need for coordinated action among a critical mass. • Building on progress made so far by reform initiatives such as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), the Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers, or the Leiden Manifesto, CoARA’s Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA), published in July 2022, establishes a common direction for research assessment reform while respecting organisations’ autonomy. It is based on shared principles, 10 commitments, and a timeframe (1 & 5 years) for reforms.
<p>Turning the Agreement into action:</p> <p>Beyond advocacy for change, ARRA signatories commit to implementing changes within their organisations. CoARA offers communities of practice to those willing to improve research assessment. These working groups aim to discuss and develop outputs that will advance research assessment and help members implement their commitments.</p>	<p>CoARA members and signatories of the ARRA engage in actions to reshape assessment practices along 10 commitments. They develop and implement their actions autonomously while communicating progress with other members and signatories and within their community, based on self-assessment.</p> <p>In practice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By year 1, organisations have communicated how they have started reviewing or developing their assessment criteria, tools, and processes in an action plan with defined milestones and in accordance with the Agreement’s 10 commitments. • By year 5, organisations have regularly demonstrated progress towards reviewing, developing, and evaluating criteria, tools and processes that fulfil the core commitments. • CoARA members also further the implementation of research assessment reforms by participating in

	<p>knowledge exchange platforms such as Working Groups and National Chapters.</p>
<p>A global coalition for systemic reform: By expanding worldwide, CoARA strives to create a diverse and impactful coalition that can effectively address the challenges of research assessment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considering the inherently global and transnational nature of research, systemic change requires the broadest possible involvement of research and research-related institutions. • CoARA is committed to advancing research assessment worldwide. By expanding the coalition internationally, CoARA strives to create a global, diverse and impactful community that can effectively address the challenges of research assessment.
<p>A community-driven effort: CoARA brings together a critical mass of stakeholders to reform research assessment from the ground up. This bottom-up approach ensures that the research communities remain in control.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CoARA, established in December 2022, is driven by the collective efforts of over 600 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and associations committed to reforming research assessment. Its bottom-up approach ensures control and ownership by the research communities. • CoARA is not a membership fee-based organisation. Members participate on a voluntary basis and contribute by implementing the 10 commitments of the Agreement within their organisation. • CoARA offers a space for its members to learn from other's experiences and to actively develop pathways in reforming research assessment by participating in communities of practice: National Chapters and Working Groups. • National Chapters are country-level implementation communities. They are created at the initiative of CoARA members and involve members on a voluntary basis.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working Groups provide mutual learning and collaboration on specific thematic research assessment areas. Participating members exchange knowledge, learn from each other’s experience, discuss and develop outputs to advance research assessment and support the implementation of members’ commitments.
<p>Core Commitment 1: Recognising the diversity of research activities, practices, outputs, and careers.</p>	<p>Purpose: This commitment will broaden recognition of the diverse practices, activities and careers in research, considering the specific nature of research disciplines and other research endeavours.</p> <p>Scope: Changes in assessment practices should enable recognition of the broad diversity of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> valuable contributions that researchers make to science and for the benefit of society, including diverse outputs beyond journal publications and irrespective of the language in which they are communicated; practices that contribute to robustness, openness, transparency, and the inclusiveness of research and the research process, including peer review, teamwork and collaboration; activities including teaching, leadership, supervision, training and mentoring. <p>It is also important that assessment facilitates the recognition and valorisation of diverse roles and careers in research, including data steward, software engineer and data scientist roles, technical roles, public outreach, science diplomacy, science advice and science communicator roles, to name a few. It is recognised that current practice is often too narrow and limiting, so the goal cannot be to replace the narrow criteria we wish to move away from with different but equally narrow criteria. Instead, the aim is to allow organisations to broaden the spectrum of what they value in research while acknowledging that this may vary across disciplines and that each individual researcher should not be expected to</p>

	<p>contribute to all activities at once.</p>
<p>Core Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: This commitment will enable the move towards research assessment criteria that focus primarily on quality while recognising that responsible use of quantitative indicators can support meaningful and relevant assessment, which is context-dependent. • Scope: Research assessment should rely primarily on qualitative assessment for which peer review is central, supported by responsibly used quantitative indicators where appropriate. Peer review is the most robust method known for assessing quality and has the advantage that it is in the hands of the research community. It is important that peer review processes are designed to meet the fundamental principles of rigour and transparency: expert assessment, transparency, impartiality, appropriateness, confidentiality, integrity and ethical considerations, gender, equality and diversity. To address the biases and imperfections to which any method is prone, the research community re-assesses and improves peer review practices regularly. Revised or potentially new criteria, tools and processes appropriate for assessing quality could be explored alongside peer review. Moving towards assessment practices that rely more heavily on qualitative methods may require additional efforts from researchers. Researchers should be recognised for these efforts and their contributions to reviewing peers' work should be valued as part of their career progression.

<p>Core Commitment 3:</p> <p>Abandon the inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular, the inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: This commitment will reduce the dominance of a narrow set of quantitative journal- and publication-based metrics. • Scope: Inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics in research assessment should be abandoned. In particular, this means moving away from using metrics like the Journal Impact Factor (JIF), Article Influence Score (AIS) and h-index as proxies for quality and impact. ‘Inappropriate uses’ include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • relying exclusively on author-based metrics (e.g. counting papers, patents, citations, grants, etc.) to assess quality and/or impact; • assessing outputs based on metrics relating to publication venue, format or language; • relying on any other metrics that do not properly capture quality and/or impact.
<p>Core Commitment 4:</p> <p>Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: This commitment will help avoid those metrics being used by international rankings, which are inappropriate for assessing researchers, trickle down to research and researcher assessment. It will help the research community and research organisations regain the autonomy to shape assessment practices, rather than having to abide by criteria and methodologies set by external commercial companies. This could include retaining control over ranking methodologies and data.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope: Recognising that the international rankings most often referred to by research organisations are currently not ‘fair and responsible’, the criteria these rankings use should not trickle down to the evaluation of individual researchers, research teams and research units. Research organisations should also be mindful that public communication (e.g. the active advertising of an institution’s rank) can contribute to the perception that research quality conflates with ranking positions. <p>Where ranking approaches are deemed unavoidable, as may be the case in forms of evaluation beyond the scope of this Agreement such as benchmarking and performance reviews of countries or institutions, the methodological limitations of such approaches should be acknowledged, and institutions should avoid trickle-down effects on research and researcher assessment.</p>
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3.2. Communication Channels and Tools

3.2.1. Website

Current structure

Figure 1 CoARA website landing page

CoARA’s website <https://coara.eu> is the backbone to CoARA Boost’s communication

activities, providing detailed information about the coalition's objectives, the ARRA commitments, CoARA's structure, news (General Assembly decisions, Working Groups and National Chapters' progress...), participation in events, academic research, and blog posts.

Developed at the onset of the coalition the website is currently structured via the following pages:

- **About:** Outlines who is behind CoARA; the agreement process
- **Agreement:** With the full text of ARRA available, a section dedicated to CoARA's commitments, Action Plans, an overview of all signatories and a FAQ
- **Coalition:** Overview of the coalition, introduction of project CoARA Boost, Steering Board, Governance, the guiding principles of CoARA, and an overview of CoARA's membership
- **Working Groups and National Chapters:** Overview of Working Groups, an overview of National Chapters, documentation and forms relating to this section, the evaluation guidelines for proposals, and a to this section dedicated FAQ
- **News:** latest updates and news related to the coalition
- **Resources:** a repository of forms and documentation such as on rules and procedures
- **Contact:** with central email addresses (communication@coara.eu for media requests, and info@coara.eu for administrative and secretarial requests) and a contact form to reach out to the CoARA Secretariat
- Link to sign up for the CoARA membership newsletter
- Link to sign the agreement and become a member of the coalition

Taking into account the evolution of CoARA's activities and the production of the first outputs stemming from its Working Groups, National Chapters, and Cascade funding projects, the structure of CoARA's website is currently being reviewed and aims to be updated by first quarter 2025.

News items

The CoARA website has a dedicated news section that provides regular updates on the ongoing implementation of CoARA, such as major events, milestones, and developments of CoARA Boost. The news articles are to be complemented by opinion pieces, best practices of assessment identified in WP3, and interviews from individual representatives of WG, NC, and SB as a means to inspire member and non-member organisations in implementing the

reform of research assessment, and strengthening CoARA’s overall discourse.

Figure 2 CoARA website news page

Domain names

In line with CoARA's ambition to expand its activities beyond European borders, the domain <https://coara.org> has been purchased and now redirects to <https://coara.eu>, including all URLs. In order to protect CoARA's reputation, additional domains such as coara.global, coara.community, and coara.international have also been acquired.

Duplication for National Chapters

To support National Chapters in their communication efforts at national level, and to ensure visual consistency of CoARA's brand

identity, the duplication of the website framework is to be provided to up to five chapters, based on their needs, as well as their members’ capacity to produce content.

At the current stage of the project, the website framework has been duplicated in French and is to be populated and maintained by the French NC, available at <https://coara.fr/>.

Figure 3 Provision of the website by the CoARA NC France

Website targets:

- 50 news items, 60K unique visitors by the end of CoARA Boost, average engagement time superior to 2mn.
- coara.org features among the top 3 references for queries related to research assessment reform.

3.2.2. Social Media

Social media channels actively promote and raise awareness for CoARA's activities, goals, and results, encouraging participation and expanding CoARA membership. CoARA is a bottom-up coalition, and its social media accounts provide a space that fosters interaction, exchange, and connection in relation to the reform of research assessment. Social media content and distribution amplify outputs of WGs and NCs, as well as the submission of Action Plans, key events, and updates on CoARA-related activities. Social media content is to include joint campaigns with related initiatives, such as DORA and ALLEA, around key dates.

#ReformingRA serves as the central hashtag for all activities concerning CoARA and the RRA, enabling users to track and engage with topics related to the reform of research assessment and CoARA. Other hashtags used to expand CoARA's outreach include #ResearchAssessment #ResearchCulture #RRA #CoARA and tailored hashtags for event purposes, e.g. #CoARainPorto.

CoARA's social media strategy prioritises LinkedIn as a primary platform for engagement, complemented by posting on X and YouTube. Following the current trends in social media, Mastodon has also been explored as an alternative channel. The engagement on each platform is closely monitored and its usage adapted accordingly.

3.2.2.1. LinkedIn

Created: 08 March 2023

URL: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/coarassessment/>

Account name: Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

Number of followers: 2,908 [27/09/2024]

Figure 4 CoARA account on LinkedIn [27/09/2024]

Metrics

Figure 5: Visibility of CoARA via LinkedIn account over time, based on impressions between 8 March 2023 and 27 September 2024

LinkedIn enables CoARA to connect with individuals, including researchers, advocates, context setters, and research assessment experts. In addition, CoARA follows and is followed by initiatives with aligned efforts and CoARA member organisations on LinkedIn. The CoARA LinkedIn community receives regular updates on the coalition's progress and developments in the research assessment reform.

Since the creation of the account on the 8th of March 2023 and until the 27th of September 2024, 235 posts and reposts were created and distributed from the CoARA LinkedIn account. CoARA has received 3,756 post reactions to date and 321 reposts of CoARA content on

LinkedIn. The top three visitor demographics to CoARA's LinkedIn page are from research (18.4%), education (15.1%), and community and social services (11.3%). CoARA's visibility has significantly increased throughout 2024, with the launch of CoARA Boost, the roll-out of the Cascade funding call, and the evolution of CoARA's working groups, and national chapters.

Targets: 5000 followers

3.2.3. X (formerly Twitter)

Created: 21 December 2022

URL: <https://twitter.com/CoARAssessment>

Account name: @CoARAssessment

Displayed name: CoARA

Number of followers: 2,548 [27/09/2024]

Figure 6 CoARA account on X [27/09/2024]

As of September 27th, 2024, 679 posts and reposts have been shared and distributed via the CoARA account with 2,550 followers.

Figure 7: Visibility of CoARA via X/Twitter account over time

Milestones will be amplified through X to create visibility peaks, resulting in increased outreach. Live posting via CoARA’s X account ensures instant communication during milestone events. In between milestones, CoARA raises awareness for its mission and activities while keeping audiences informed of developments in research assessment reform. Repostings of projects that are in line with RRA efforts will help foster closer collaboration and increase outreach.

3.2.4. Mastodon

Created: 27 November 2023

URL: <https://mastodon.social/@CoARAssessment>

Account name: @CoARAssessment

Displayed name: CoARA

Number of followers: 77 [27/09/2024]

As of February 28th, 2024, there have been 71 posts published and reposted on Mastodon.

Figure 8 CoARA account on Mastodon [28/02/2024]

Following the change in ownership of the Twitter/X platform, a Mastodon account aims to tap into users who have migrated from Twitter to extend the reach of CoARA content.

3.2.5. YouTube

Created: 17 April 2023

URL: www.youtube.com/@CoARAssessment

Account name: @CoARAssessment

Displayed name: CoARA Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

Number of subscribers: 84 [27/09/2024]

Number of views: 2,684 [27/09/2024]

Figure 9 CoARA account on YouTube [25/07/2024]

CoARA's YouTube channel is primarily a repository for various types of videos related to webinars, presentations, conferences, and CoARA's vision, mission, and work. Annotations link to additional content, such as a website. CoARA's videos are shared on various social networks and CoARA communication channels, adding value to other communication releases and making the consumption of information more engaging by combining various media.

3.3. Newsletters

Since February 2024, newsletters have been issued by email to CoARA members to keep them informed of the latest developments within the coalition. The newsletter is circulated to all registered CoARA contact points of member organisations.

Subscription is open to individuals from CoARA member organisations through a form embedded on the website and linked to a Mailchimp platform.

The newsletter audience list currently has 1,687 subscribers.

Figure 10 Website main menu allocation of newsletter registration

Contents include the following:

- CoARA milestones and news, including from CoARA Boost
- Coalition's membership developments
- News from the General Assemblies, Steering Board, National Chapters and Working Groups
- Upcoming events related to research assessment reform
- Research assessment reform highlights

Issues previously released:

- [Issue #1, February 2024](#)
- [Issue #2, May 2024](#)
- [Issue #3, September 2024](#)

Figure 11 First newsletter issue

To expand the reach of these newsletters beyond the email subscribers within member organisations, they are additionally edited as LinkedIn newsletters. Followers of CoARA’s account are invited to subscribe to CoARA’s LinkedIn newsletters; subscribers receive a push notification and email after each new edition of the page newsletter.

3.4. Videos

CoARA Boost will enhance the promotion of CoARA’s activities through the production of videos. An initial video is to provide stakeholders with an overview of the ARRA commitments and CoARA’s scope, inviting more members to sign and join the coalition. At a later stage, a set of short-format videos will provide insights on the implementation of research assessment reform.

3.5. Webinars

Regular webinars are organised within WP2, WP3, WP4 and in collaboration with CoARA working groups. They aim to provide support in applying to the calls for cascade funding, in developing action plans, or to present progress within WG.

Recorded webinars are made publicly available via [CoARA’s YouTube channel](#).

3.6. Press Releases

Press releases are distributed at significant project milestones, such as project launches, funding calls, new working groups, and noteworthy events, with the aim of disseminating crucial project-related news and raising awareness among stakeholders.

They are circulated to CoARA’s members and disseminated to local, national, global, and specialised media. Past issues include:

- Launch of CoARA
- [CoARA membership exceeds 500 members](#), 13 June 2023
- [Launch of cascade funding, 26 April 2024](#)

3.7. Media relations

As the creation and development of CoARA leads to debates relayed by the media, CoARA Boost puts efforts into ensuring that key messages related to CoARA and ARRA are correctly communicated. Latest examples of press clippings include:

[Global movement to reform researcher assessment gains traction](#), *Physics Today*, 1 October 2023

[“The role of scientometrics in the pursuit of responsible research assessment”](#), *LSE Blog*, 4 September 2024

[“Assessment reform group defends move away from metrics”](#), *Research Professional News*, 10 September 2024

[Emerging Coara national groups push for a 'real culture change'](#), *Research Professional News*, 7 March 2024

4. Dissemination and engagement

Building on the communication and awareness-raising activities, dissemination aims to stimulate the uptake of the project's results by key players and context setters by inspiring, supporting, and engaging them to implement change in research assessment practices. The following activities and tools will namely focus on disseminating:

- Signatories' action plans and mapping of members' practices (under WP3).
- Outputs from WG, NC, and cascade funding projects, including guidelines and recommendations, collections of good practices, reports from pilots, white papers, reports from workshops or conferences, toolkits...
- Lessons learned and recommendations issued from assessment practices and mappings, WG.

4.1. Publications

4.1.1. Open Access

In line with its core values, CoARA Boost ensures that all the publications issued by its members, WG, funded projects, and SB remain openly available. The primary repositories for providing content and innovations publicly available are Zenodo and the CoARA website. Additionally, interviews given by CoARA SB members to publication outlets will be given on condition that they will result in openly accessible articles.

4.1.1.1. Zenodo

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. Free to upload and free to access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term.¹ The platform constitutes the main repository for CoARA publications, ensuring a broad and long-term accessibility.

- The main [CoARA Community](#) features overall presentations and publications related to the coalition.
- The [CoARA Action Plans](#) community hosts the collection of ARRA signatories' action

¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo-guide>

plans, in line with their commitment to share these publicly.

- As for the [CoARA National Chapters Exchange Forum 2024](#), presentations given within events organised by CoARA are made accessible on a specific Zenodo community.
- As part of the CoARA Zenodo portfolio, there is also a [dedicated hub for outputs of Working Groups](#).
- Finally, there is also a [collection dedicated to the CoARA Boost project deliverables and outputs](#)
- The Zenodo architecture allows for easy linking of outputs into multiple collections and therefore these subgroups are complementing each other and linking to multiple collections can easily be accommodated.

Figure 12 CoARA Zenodo Community

4.1.2. Policy Briefs

In line with Horizon Europe requirements, CoARA Boost will produce two policy briefs (M12 and M30). The first policy brief will aim to translate insights from the first WG and preliminary mapping of assessment practices into actionable intelligence for the implementation of reformed research assessment practices.

The second policy brief will provide content for policymaking at the EU and international levels, aiming to provide input to the European Commission for the next policy cycle.

4.2. Conferences and Events

4.2.1. Organisation of Conferences

Two high-level conferences will be organised as in-person events to disseminate the

outputs of the working groups and the CoARA Boost project.

The [first conference took place on 10–11 September in Helsinki, Finland](#), as a forum for the co-chairs of the 13 WGs. Participants engaged in a series of presentations and discussions focusing on the progress, challenges, and synergies among CoARA Working Groups. Topics included enhancing collaboration across thematic areas, aligning efforts with national research strategies, and setting framework for endorsing Working Groups' outputs.

Figure 13: Promotion of CoARA's event on WGs

CoARA Boost concludes with a final conference, planned in M34 to showcase the project outputs and maximise its impact on research assessment reform and engage a broad audience. The exact timing and location will be decided during the project, to achieve maximum impact.

4.2.2. Participation in internal events

CoARA Boost also capitalises on in-person and online events organised by CoARA members to disseminate the coalition's outputs.

Figure 14: Promotion of a call to host CoARA events

The CoARA National Chapters Exchange Forum was held in Porto, Portugal, from February 22 to 23, 2024. High-level representatives participated in the event from 15 CoARA National Chapters. In total the event was attended by 80 participants onsite, and 40 attendees online.

[A call to host further NC and WG events](#) has been launched among CoARA members to support CoARA's operational capacity and provide further dissemination opportunities and platforms to explore synergies, to engage in mutual learning and capacity building.

CoARA's General Assembly is convened bi-annually

online and provides a forum for all CoARA members to come together and discuss the progress of the coalition.

4.2.3. Participation in external events

Steering Board Members, CoARA Boost partners, as well as WG and NC co-chairs are actively involved in presenting CoARA, its activities and outputs within conferences. Participation aims to raise awareness for the need to reform research assessment, increase the coalition's membership, and promote the project's outputs that operationalise the implementation of reform.

Opportunities for participation by for Steering Board members in high-reach events are continuously identified and coordinated by the Secretariat.

A selected subset of presentations is made available on Zenodo.

4.3. Dissemination through relays

As CoARA's membership grows, creating further gravitas to promote the reform of research assessment, its "Key players", as described above, play a crucial role in expanding the reach of its communication dissemination activities within their internal and external networks, to achieve a multiplying effect.

Figure 15 Multiplier Effect

Figure 16 Levels of Awareness CoARA Boost

4.3.1. Signatory and member organisations

Figure 17: CoARA Advocacy Badge

CoARA members are core vectors in disseminating the project's outputs. As they sign the ARRA and join the coalition, members indicate the name and details of a point of contact responsible for relaying news and outputs from CoARA within their institution. Upon signature, members are also invited to provide the details of an [institutional communication contact](#) in order to support their efforts to reach out to their internal and external stakeholders. Members and signatories are encouraged to promote their engagement in CoARA through their institutional communication channels with the **provision of a communication kit**,

including the CoARA logo and guidelines, a ready-to-use PPT presentation of CoARA, and an **"advocacy badge"**.

The strong network of communication relays will continually receive information and updates on CoARA's progress. This mechanism will enhance the dissemination to their organisation's staff, researchers, students, and external stakeholders.

4.3.1.1. Commitment to promote their Action Plan

Signatory organisations agree to share with each other and with their community how their organisation has started the process of reviewing or developing criteria, tools and processes in line with the core Commitments and according to an action plan with defined milestones, within one year of signing the Agreement. As detailed in the Publication section, they are invited to upload it on the dedicated Zenodo community as a means to inspire other organisations.

4.3.2. National Chapters

The NC provide a forum at national levels for organisations involved in research to put the CoARA principles into practice. Their events, meetings and other activities provide a sounding board for the promotion of the ARRA and CoARA's outputs towards their member organisations, as well to ministries and non-member organisations. They also participate in raising awareness about CoARA in national media.

As NC are being established and are implementing their activities, a certain number have developed a dedicated website:

- [France](#)
- [Italy](#)

CoARA Boosts supports the NC in their dissemination efforts by providing them with a [page on the coalition's website](#) featuring an overall description, including main objectives, activities, and members. As the number of NC grows, CoARA Boost will support a limited number of NC by providing a duplicated version of the coalition's website, as a framework to develop their own website in consistency with CoARA's visual guidelines.

4.3.3. Working Group members

With a strong involvement in CoARA and the implementation of the reform of research assessment, WG members and co-chairs are also active in promoting the need for research assessment reform and CoARA's scope, and in disseminating its outputs.

At this stage of the deliverable, the endorsement process for the outputs from the WG are currently still being defined. The dissemination strategy for these outputs will be adapted accordingly.

4.3.4. Cascade funding beneficiaries

The call for cascading projects is widely promoted within CoARA's members and beyond to ensure numerous and high-quality applications. The developments and results of the funded projects will equally be made accessible in data repositories (Zenodo) and on CoARA's website and promoted for further research or implementation.

Cascade funding beneficiaries will ensure to have a clear dissemination plan of their outputs and explicitly acknowledge their funding by CoARA Boost and the European Commission. They will also be encouraged to promote the Coalition and its Agreement through the recipients' corporate channels.

4.3.5. Umbrella organisations as advocates

CoARA Boost aims to reach out to key players beyond CoARA members, such as context

setters and advocates. To achieve this, successful dissemination activities will be conducted through its partners' extensive network, including researchers, universities, academies, research organisations, research funding organisations, and umbrella organisations such as MCAA, ALLEA, YERUN and Science Europe. In addition, CoARA Boost leverages strong relationships with networks associated with the Steering Board members and observers, as well as with the other related initiatives described in section 2.3.4.

4.3.6. Membership management tool

Dissemination and engagement with communication and dissemination relays will be facilitated by the setup of a membership management tool under WP2, which will include file-sharing, discussion modules, synchronisation with the newsletter edition platform, and providing the possibility to categorise members according to their involvement in CoARA.

5. Exploitation

The purpose of CoARA Boost is to enhance the operational capacity of CoARA and provide means to investigate and implement new models for research assessment. By amplifying its spectrum of actions and providing the additional capacity to implement a Cascade funding programme, CoARA Boost allows to develop a critical mass for reforming research assessment, generate gravitas for new members and facilitate the leveraging of additional sources of funding.

By the end of the project, CoARA Boost will have catalysed the production of a considerable key exploitable results, including outputs mainly issued from its Members and signatories (Action Plans) the National Chapters, the Working Groups (such as guidelines, recommendations, tools, white papers, publications...), and from the cascade-funded projects (aiming to develop, pilot and implement, assessment criteria, tools and processes). An endorsement framework for Working Groups outputs and other CoARA endorsed resources is being discussed with the CoARA General Assembly at the time of writing the current deliverable. Conclusions of this discussion will be captured in an updated version of the current document.

In addition CoARA Boost produces two policy briefs.

As described in section 4.1.1., the outputs will stay available beyond the project lifetime open access.

Rooted in the design of the coalition, exploitation happens right from the onset, as signatory and member organisations develop their action plans, engage in mutual learning through involvement in national chapters, and are directly involved in the production of outputs through participation in working groups.

All resources, including the results of the cascade funding projects, will not only be taken up by CoARA members, but they will also be put forward for exploitation by non-member organisations, in Europe and beyond. Efforts in WP6 will specifically be undertaken to promote the use of CoARA WG outputs towards global initiatives (e.g. GRC, UNESCO), complemented with advocacy activities to extend CoARA’s reach at a global scale.

Exploitation will also be considered at the level of policymaking, in particular by means of participation in the ERA Forum, to ensure that CoARA’s recommendations and policy briefs are taken up as input in the next EU policy cycle. National Chapters and the work implemented in WP6 will support this targeted effort. Supportive actions will include online bilateral meetings, consultations, and the organisation of the final event.

At level of the project and of the coalition, potential scenarios will be explored to sustain and advance CoARA beyond the initial five years of the implementation phase. This will involve updating objectives, determining the required support, and identifying viable funding approaches. The coalition, created independently of CoARA Boost, has the potential to be maintained long-term.

5.1. Monitoring: Metrics and KPIs

Quantifiable key performance indicators (KPIs) are developed to monitor and evaluate communication and dissemination progress and impact. These metrics serve as a tool to measure the effectiveness of the communication strategy and ensure that it aligns with the CoARA’s overall goals. Tracking KPIs aims to gain insights into the efficacy of CoARA’s communication efforts and make informed decisions to optimise these efforts. This approach enables CoARA to make data-driven decisions, optimise communication channels, and improve communication outcomes. CoARA’s dissemination methods, KPI targets and strategy measures are presented in the table below.

Channel	KPI(s)	Target(s)	Strategy
Website	Site visits (page + screen views per month)	60K users	The CoARA website is ranked as the top reference for research assessment queries (SEO optimisation). Regular updates and news items on the website.
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Followers ▪ Impressions 	4000 150k	Increased posts mentioning hashtags. Cross-media content to make posts more

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reactions (end of project) 	5000	engaging. Impressions & Followers indicate outreach of CoARA. Reactions to measure the increased quality of engagement of social media followers.
X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Followers 	4000	Increased posts mentioning hashtags. Cross-media content to make posts more engaging.
YouTube	Views (end of project)	4000	Its primary function as a repository for various types of videos, cross-posted and disseminated on other channels, therefore views main KPI, and not subscriber.
Newsletter	Subscribers (end of project)	2500	Anyone from CoARA member organisations can subscribe to the newsletter, which is also promoted on the website and encouraged to be circulated within the organisation. The newsletter is issued quarterly.
Policy briefs	No. of peer-reviewed publications	2	Two policy briefs.
Press Releases	No. of releases (end of project)	8	Sent to local and national media. Press clippings in high-reach media.
Repository of Assessment Practices	No. of registries (end of project)	500	Zenodo, publication of Action Plans and Working Group outcomes. Promotion via various communication channels.
Participation in high-reach international	No. of events (end of project)	6	Collaboration with WP6. M8 GYA in Washington D.C., more tbd.

events			
Conference	No. of events (end of project)	2	One conference and one CoARA Boost final event.

Table 1 Dissemination Metrics

5.2. Alignment with Project Partners

To foster effective collaboration among the consortium partners, collaboration channels facilitate a consistent flow of relevant information, leading to better collaboration and desired outcomes. Maintaining open communication channels and providing regular updates to partners is equally important to ensure the success of the project.

An internal collaborative Activities Plan helps partners stay informed on ongoing actions. The listed actions inform the communications plan and aid in understanding needs, target audiences, and channel selection for delivering messages.

5.3. Reflection Points: Strategy Adaption

5.3.1. Global and Local Considerations

CoARA Boost intends to move CoARA towards a globally recognised coalition. Besides the visibility on a global scale, adaption to cultural layers will manifest a central venture for the coalition's success. A multilingual CoARA is a key theme under CoARA's globalisation strategy. To support this evolvement, up to 5 National Chapters will be supported with the provision of the website framework for translation in local languages upon request.

5.3.2. Social Media Fast-paced Environment

The social media environment is fast-paced and under constant change. Between the grant agreement and the development of this DEC strategy, the ownership from formerly Twitter has moved towards X. During project CoARA Boost, it is expected that algorithms of social media platforms will change, affecting the display of and engagement with content. Also, user behaviour and landscapes might shift, and once as suitable and reasonably identified, platforms supportive of CoARA see fewer advantage points while others gain in relevance. Therefore, it is expected that decisions on changes need to be made during the project lifetime, therefore, justifiable strategy adaptations.

6. Acknowledgment of EU Funding

All recipients of CoARA Boost have the legal obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received funding EU funding to ensure visibility and transparency.

The obligation requires all beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of CoARA Boost to display prominently the EU emblem and funding statement on all the communication materials (including electronic communication, using social media, etc.) and dissemination activities. It also applies to any equipment, infrastructure, vehicle, supply or result financed by the grant, and all types of public outputs such as patent applications, standardisation of results, contacts with the media and other public statements.

How to display the EU emblem and funding statement

**Funded by
the European Union**

Figure 18: EU funding acknowledgment

Make sure to display the European flag (official EU emblem). Add the funding statement next to the official EU emblem (in local languages, where appropriate).

Disclaimer

The following disclaimer shall be added, in addition to the EU emblem:

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.

7. Appendices

CoARA Boost communication and dissemination activities build on CoARA's visual identity. Consistent branding helps to establish recognition of CoARA, increase its visibility, and generate interest in the coalition. Additionally, a communication toolbox consisting of templates, standard presentation slide decks, and other resources is provided to partners to help them maintain consistency with CoARA's visual identity.

7.1. Visual identity

7.1.1. CoARA logo

Figure 19 Logo symbols

Figure 20: CoARA Logo with title

Figure 21: CoARA logo without title

7.1.2. Colour Scheme and Font

Figure 22 Primary Colours

Figure 23 Secondary Colours

Figure 24 Fonts

8. Templates

8.1. Presentations

Figure 25: CoARA PowerPoint Presentation Template

8.2. Social Media Posts

Figure 26: LinkedIn Newsletter Post

Figure 27: Post on ERA Conference